

Dapsone induced neutropenic sepsis in a patient with immune mediated thrombocytopenia

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ABSTRACT Dapsone rarely causes agranulocytosis which is severe toxic effect of the sulfones. It is usually reversible condition; however, it can lead to sepsis and even death. There are few cases with agranulocytosis due to dapsone in literature. Here, we reported neutropenic sepsis with an array of complications due to dapsone, in a patient treated for resistant immune-mediated thrombocytopenia which to the best of our knowledge is the first such report in Sri Lanka.

KEYWORDS Dapsone, neutropenia, sepsis, genital ulcer

Introduction

Dapsone is used for the treatment of resistant immune-mediated thrombocytopenia, leprosy, Pneumocystis jiroveci pneumonia, dermatitis herpetiformis, chronic bullous dermatosis and malaria prophylaxis [1]. It can cause several mild to severe, life-threatening adverse effects in which agranulocytosis is a rare, fatal complication of dapsone, leading to sepsis and even death. Here, we reported neutropenic sepsis in a patient treated with dapsone for resistant immune-mediated thrombocytopenia.

Case Report

A 44-years-old housewife presented to a tertiary care hospital in Sri Lanka with fever and painful perineal ulcers for three days duration. She was previously diagnosed with immune-mediated thrombocytopenia and was on prednisolone 7.5 mg daily for a one-year duration. She was treated with dapsone recently for four weeks for resistant immune-mediated thrombocytopenia. On examination, she was febrile and had multiple painful superficial blistering genital ulcers and a diffuse erythematous, tender, swelling at right side upper medial part of thigh suggestive of genital herpes with an abscess. His pulse rate was 100/min with a blood pressure of 100/70mmHg. Rest of systemic examination was unremarkable. Her complete blood count showed

severe neutropenia (26%) with leucopenia (1240/mm³) where initial white cell count was normal (8760/mm³ with 70% neutrophils) before the commencement of dapsone therapy one month back. Her serial white cell count and blood other investigations were shown in Table 1. Multinucleated giant cells were detected in the microscopical analysis of the sample taken from the ulcers. HSV type 2 antibodies were positive of samples taken from the ulcers. Her retroviral screening such as HIV and VDRL and septic screening were negative. A diagnosis of genital herpes in an immunocompromised secondary state probably due to dapsone was made. Given neutropenia, Dapsone was discontinued, and the patient was started on broad-spectrum intravenous meropenem 1g three times daily and intravenous acyclovir 500mg three times daily. She was also treated with filgrastim for three consecutive days due to further dropping neutrophil count. A progressive clinical recovery was observed in the patient and a simultaneous rise in her white cell count on the 8th day of therapy.

She was managed with high dose prednisolone subsequently with monitoring her blood count serially. She completely recovered with therapy with normal cell count and followed at a medical clinic.

Discussion

Dapsone, the prototype of sulfones rarely causes agranulocytosis which is severe toxic effect of the sulfones. It is characterized by a low concentration or absence of granulocytes due to sulfone cytotoxicity effects on bone marrow and mononuclear cells leaving the body susceptible to bacterial invasion and septicemia [2]. An occurrence of 0.2-0.4% of agranulocytosis was described in the literature with dapsone therapy [3]. It is usually reversible condition; however, it can lead to sepsis and even death [4].

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Table 1 The pattern of blood investigations following dapsone-induced neutropenic sepsis.

Investigations	Before Dapsone therapy	Day 1	Day 3	Day 5	Day 7	Day 10	Day 14	Day 21	Follow-up
WBC count (mm ³)	6,340	1,240	930	6,20	1,180	2,570	4,830	9,210	8,490
Neutrophils (%)	58	50	30	10	40	170	1700	5310	5020
Lymphocytes (%)	37	1000	1380	730	930	1950	2980	3390	2860
Platelet count (mm ³)	179,000	150,000	282,000	323,000	538,000	502,000	55,100	18,000	103,000
AST (u/l)	32	36	34	32	37	35	42	36	29
ALT (u/l)	28	30	32	48	43	31	36	31	36
CRP (mg/l)	35	245	298	286	215	189	139	79	32
ESR (mm/1st hour)	53	76	79	86	96	98	89	76	34
Serum Creatinine (umol/l)	52	68	67	76	62	73	86	65	54
Blood Culture	-	-	Sterile	-	Sterile	-	Sterile	-	-
Urine Culture	-	-	Sterile	-	Sterile	-	Sterile	-	-

Abbreviations: WBC; White cell count, AST: Aspartate transaminase, ALT: Alanine transaminase, CRP: C reactive protein, ESR: Erythrocyte sedimentation rate.

Dapsone is a structural analogue of para-aminobenzoic acid that acts as a competitive inhibitor of dihydropteroate synthase in the folate metabolic pathway. The formation of antibodies against neutrophil progenitor cells and the sensitization to the drug that forms hydroxylamine are responsible mechanisms for agranulocytosis and methemoglobinemia and hemolysis [4]. It has a wide range of pharmacodynamic properties such as anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antiprotozoal, and antifungal activities which are indicated of dapsone in clinical practices for the treatment of leprosy, malaria, granuloma annulare, dermatitis herpetiformis, and other vesiculobullous diseases [1]. It is commonly used to treat immune thrombocytopenic patients drug in Sri Lanka, especially for those who are refractory to steroids due to its effectiveness and low cost. However, it causes several adverse effects such as hemolytic anaemia, methemoglobinemia, agranulocytosis, hepatitis, peripheral neuropathy, nephrotic syndrome and dapsone syndrome [3]. Agranulocytosis is a rare, serious complication caused by the myelotoxic effect of these drugs which is non-dose-related, usually occurs between 3 weeks and three months after the onset of therapy [4, 5]. The complete blood count should be monitored weekly for the first month of therapy, twice per month for the next two months, and periodically to detect the complication early [5]. Hepatic and renal function tests should also be conducted before the initiation of therapy and periodically later. However, the rarity of this complication makes such testing challenging to follow as a routine. The patient should be advised about the risk of infection and to seek medical advice if fever during the initial phase of dapsone therapy.

Our patient had severe agranulocytosis, and she developed genital herpes with abscess secondary to dapsone therapy. Dapsone had to be discontinued due to side effects in such conditions. The treatments continued with antibiotic therapy and filgrastim revealing leucometric and clinical improvement in a

few days [5]. In our patient, withdrawal of offending drug and early treatment with antibiotics and G-CSF accounted for the survival of the patient. Mortality in different case reports with dapsone therapy has been 20%. This fatal condition should be diagnosed early and treated by physicians accordingly as early measures can be life-saving for the patient. There are several individual reports of dapsone therapy with hypersensitivity syndrome, hemolytic anaemia and fewer cases with agranulocytosis due to dapsone in literature. Here, we report a patient with an array of complications due to dapsone, which to the best of our knowledge is the first such report in Sri Lanka.

Competing Interests

None

Funding

None

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